

Factors Related To Learning Achievement in Elementary School Children (SD) in North Balikpapan District, 2019

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Abstract— School children are a very important state asset as human resources for the success of national development. School children are children aged 7-12 years, have a stronger physical individual characteristics and are active and not dependent on parents. School children are a very important state asset as human resources for the success of national development. Good nutritional status will affect the process of growth and development of children, one of which can improve intellectual abilities that will have an impact on learning achievement in school. Malnutrition can cause some serious effects such as failure of physical growth, decreased intelligence development and decreased resistance to disease and increased risk of morbidity and death. This study aims to determine the relationship between nutritional status with learning achievement in elementary school children (SDN). The benefit of this research is to produce enrichment of teaching materials, scientific works which are published in national journals and as a source of information for the community about good nutritional status so as to produce good learning achievements in school children. The type of research carried out in this study is Analytic descriptive, with cross sectional design, that is data concerning the dependent variable and the independent variable are collected and observed at the same time. This research was carried out in elementary schools located in the district of North Balikpapan, with a population of 9 elementary schools and 2 primary schools. The sample of this study is school children aged 7-12 years, the estimated size of the sample used in this study uses the formula. Univariate analysis is performed with descriptive analysis to see the characteristics of each variable studied. Bivariate analysis was performed using the Chi Square test (χ^2) to determine the relationship of each independent variable with related variables.

Keywords— School children, Nutritional status, Interests, Motivation For Learning, Attitude, Elementary School Children's Achievement.

I. INTRODUCTION

The success of the development of a nation is very dependent on the success of the nation itself in preparing quality, healthy, intelligent and productive human resources. However rich natural resources are available to a nation without strong human resources, it is difficult to expect to succeed in building the nation itself (Hadi, 2005).

Nutrition is one of the important factors that determine the level of health and harmony between physical development and mental development. The level of normal nutritional status is reached when optimal nutritional requirements are met. A person's nutritional level in a period is not only determined by the consumption of nutrients in the past. Malnutrition can cause some serious effects such as failure of physical growth, decreased intelligence development. Nutrition is needed by school children for growth and development, energy, thinking, and endurance. Quality nutrition will optimize the growth and development of the brain. Good nutritional status will affect the process of growth and development of children, one of which can improve intellectual abilities that will have an impact on learning achievement in school (Soemirat, 2009).

Nutrition fulfillment factors determine the success of children in the learning process. Some parents only assume that if children study hard they will get relatively high learning outcomes. In fact, there are many other factors that influence children's learning outcomes, especially for students who are

still sitting in low class. Where physical health is still very influential. Children who get good nutritional fulfillment from their families tend to be motivated to learn even though the intelligence factor owned by these students is low (Soemirat, 2009).

Children who suffer from malnutrition will result in reduced catchment, decreased concentration of learning, physical growth is not optimal, tend to be a short child's posture, children are not actively moving, weak immune system so it is susceptible to disease and affect the work capacity as an adult. One of the factors that influence learning achievement is the level of intelligence. Intelligence is closely related to the level of growth and development of brain cells, and food influences the development of brain cells (Soemirat, 2009).

Nadharatunna'im et al. (2014) conducted a study of the relationship between nutritional status and learning achievement. The results of the study showed that there was a significant relationship between nutritional status and learning achievement, where it was found that students with poor nutritional status with less academic achievement totaled 13 people (29.5%) and those with good learning achievement and nutritional status were 6 (13, 6%), while students with sufficient nutritional status with less learning achievement totaled 7 people (15.9%) and good learning achievement with adequate nutritional status totaling 18 people (40.9%). The results of a study conducted by Rosa (2015) on the effect of attitudes on chemistry subjects and self-concepts on chemistry

learning achievement, obtained results that student learning attitudes on chemistry subjects and self-concepts influence on chemistry learning achievement.

Based on the description above, researchers are interested in conducting research on the factors associated with learning achievement in elementary school children in the North Balikpapan District in 2019.

II. METHODS

This type of research conducted in this study is descriptive analytic, with cross sectional design, namely data concerning the dependent variable and independent variables are collected and observed at the same time. The cross sectional design was used based on the research objectives, namely to analyze the factors associated with learning achievement in elementary school children in the North Balikpapan District in 2019.

This research was conducted at an elementary school in the North Balikpapan area and in the working area of the Muara Rapak Community Health Center. The time of implementation will be from August to October 2019.

The population in this study were all elementary schools in the area of Muara Rapak Health Center, which amounted to 9 schools. Because of the many limitations in conducting research, it will be taken a sample of the entire population. The sample is part of the number and characteristics possessed by the population, so that the results of the research conclusions can be generalized to the entire population, then the sample taken must be truly representative (Sugiono, 2012), the larger the sample of the size of the existing population the better, however there are a minimum number of limits that must be taken by researchers that is as many as 30 samples. As stated by Baley in Mahmud (2011) which states that for studies using statistical data analysis, the minimum sample size is 30. The sample in this study amounted to 95 respondents.

Determination of the number of samples is done by using the Slovin formula because in sampling, the numbers must be representative so that the results of the study can be generalized and the calculations do not require a table of sample sizes, but can be done with formulas and simple calculations (Sugiono, 2012).

III. RESULTS

A. Analisis Univariat

Univariate analysis of each variable is displayed in the form of a frequency distribution. The univariate analysis results obtained are as follows:

1. Nutritional status

TABLE 1: Overview of Nutritional Status of Elementary School Children (SD) in Balikpapan Utara District, Balikpapan City in 2019

Nutritional Status	Total	Persentase
Malnutrition (<-3)	1	1.1
Good Nutrition (-2 - 2)	94	98.9
Total	95	100.0

Source: Primary Data 2019

Based on the table above, it can be seen that the description of the nutritional status of respondents reported that the majority of good nutrition is 98.9%.

2. Interests

TABLE 2: Descriptions of Learning Interests in Elementary School Children (SD) in Balikpapan Utara District, Balikpapan City in 2019

Interests	Total	Persentase
Not interested	72	75.8
Interested	23	24.2
Total	95	100.0

Source: Primary Data 2019

Based on the table above, it can be seen that most respondents' interest in learning is not interested in learning, which is 72 (75.8%), while interested in learning as much as 23 (24.2%).

3. Motivation For Learning

TABLE 3: Descriptions of Learning Motivation in Elementary School Children (SD) in Balikpapan Utara District, Balikpapan City in 2019

Motivation to learn	Total	Persentase
Less	50	52.6
Good	45	47.4
Total	95	100.0

Source: Primary Data 2019

Based on the table above, it can be seen that the majority of respondents' attitudes or 77 (81.1%) are in the good category and 18 (18.9%) less attitudes.

4. Attitude

TABLE 4: Descriptions of Attitudes in Elementary School Children (SD) in Balikpapan Utara District, Balikpapan City in 2019

Attitude	Total	Persentase
Less	18	18.9
Good	77	81.1
Total	110	100.0

Source: Primary Data 2019

Based on the table above, it can be seen that the majority of respondents' attitudes or 77 (81.1%) are in the good category and 18 (18.9%) less attitudes.

5. Elementary School Children's Achievement

TABLE 5: Descriptions of Learning Achievement in Elementary School Children (SD) in Balikpapan Utara District, Balikpapan City in 2019

Learning achievement	Total	Persentase
Not Achieving	18	18.9
Achievers	77	81.1
Total	95	100.0

Source: Primary Data 2019

Based on the table above it can be seen that most of the respondents' learning achievements or 77 people (81.1%) in the achievement category, and as many as 18 people did not perform (18.9%).

B. Analisis Bivariat

Bivariate analysis conducted in this study aims to determine the relationship between independent variables of learning achievement with the dependent variable, namely the status of interest, motivation, talent and nutritional status. The

statistical test used was a chi-square test with an OR calculation with 95% CI.

After univariate analysis, bivariate analysis is then performed to determine the relationship between nutritional status and growth and development status of children using a chi square (X²) statistical test with a 95% confidence level.

TABLE 6: Factors affecting the learning achievement of elementary school children in Balikpapan Utara District, Balikpapan City in 2019

Variable	Learning achievement	
	P-Value	CI 95%
Motivation	0,000	.00-.00
Attitude	0,000	.00-.00
Interest	0,000	.00-.00
Nutrition	0,000	.00-.00

Source: Primary Data 2019

Based on the table above that the square test results between the dependent variable with the independent variable shows the p-value <0.05 or significantly the learning achievement variable is influenced by factors of motivation, attitude, interest and nutritional status. To find out which dependent variable is the most influential, multivariate test is continued.

C. Analisis Multivariati

TABLE 7: Logistic Regression to Know the Factors Most Influential to Elementary School Student Learning Achievement

Variabel	Learning achievement
	Sig
Motivation	.412
Attitude	.627
Interest	.000
Nutrition	.008
Total	.000

Based on the table above, it can be seen that the logistic regression test results obtained p-value (<0.25), namely the variable of interest in learning achievement, namely p = 0,000 (<0.25), the nutritional variable of learning achievement, p = 0.008 (<0.25), and the variable report cards on learning achievement is p = 0,000 (<0.25). so it can be concluded that elementary school students' learning achievement is influenced by factors of interest, report cards and children's nutritional status.

IV. DISCUSSION

A. Learning Achievement

Based on the results of research on 95 elementary school children (SD) respondents who attend SDN in the working area of Muara Rapak Health Center showed that most of the Children's Learning Achievement were 77 respondents (81.1%) and those with less or no achievement were 18 respondents (18.9%). Learning Achievement is a person's ability to achieve high thinking. Learning achievement must have three aspects, namely cognitive, affective and psychomotor. Learning according to the view of cognitive theory is defined as a process to build one's perception of an object being seen (Zainal, 2014).

According to Gagne (1977) in (Komalasari, 2013) defines that learning as a process of behavior change which includes

changes in human tendencies such as attitudes, interests or values and changes in its ability to increase the ability to perform various types of performance (performance). According to Tukiran, et al (2013) learning achievement is a part of this, namely with regard to test results that reflect students' ability to master the material. Student learning achievement is the result that has been achieved by students obtained from the learning process. Learning Achievement is also the result of maximum achievement according to the ability of children at a certain time to something that is done, learned, understood and applied.

According to Sumadi (2006) achievement can also be defined as the value of the last formulation that can be given by the teacher regarding the progress / student achievement during a certain period. So, achievement is the result of student effort during a certain period of activities. In the opinion of Hutabarat (1995), learning outcomes are divided into four groups, namely: Knowledge (information material, facts, ideas, beliefs, procedures, laws, rules, standards, and other concepts), Ability (ability to analyze, reproduce, create, arrange , summarize, make generalizations, think rationally and adapt), habits and skills (behavioral habits and skills in using all abilities, and the last is attitude (a form of appreciation, interest, consideration and taste) Learning achievement is the result of student efforts that can be achieved in the form of mastery of knowledge, habitual abilities and skills as well as attitudes after following the learning process that can be proven by the results of the test, learning achievement is something that students need to know the abilities they get from an activity called learning.

Based on the Chi square statistical test between the dependent variable and the independent variable shows the p-value <0.05 or significantly the learning achievement variable is influenced by motivational factors, attitudes, nutritional status, and report card grades. This means that the learning achievements obtained by SDN students in the working area of the Muara Rapak Public Health Center, which are mostly achievers (81.1%) are strongly influenced by the interest of students who are partially interested (75.8%) in the learning process in the class or repeating lessons in home, but there are also students whose interests are very good (24.2%). Then when viewed from the attitude, some students are moderate (80%) meaning they follow the lessons in class as usual and if there is homework they still do homework individually or in groups. When viewed from the motivation to learn, the majority of student motivation is lacking (52.6%), so there are some students who do not achieve (18.9%).

Nutrition is needed by school children for growth and development of energy, thinking, and endurance. Quality nutrition will optimize the growth and development of the brain. Good nutritional status will affect the process of growth and development of children, one of which can improve intellectual abilities that will have an impact on learning achievement in school. Malnutrition can cause some serious effects such as failure of physical growth, decreased intelligence development (Soemirat, 2009). Based on the Chi square statistical test between the dependent variable and the independent variable showing a p-value <0.05 or significantly

the learning achievement variable is influenced by nutritional status, this is consistent with the results of research conducted by Arfines and Puspitasi (2017) which states that children with poor / poor nutritional status are associated with low levels of learning achievement in school children. In this study, most respondents were of good nutrition status (98.9%) and achievers (81.1%).

B. Factors that Influence Learning Achievement

1. Nutritional status

Based on the results of research on 95 respondents Elementary School (SD) children who attend elementary school in North Balikpapan Subdistrict shows that most children are well nourished as many as 94 respondents (98.9%) and there is only 1 person who has undernourished (1.1%). When viewed from the learning achievement ank, then most children achievers (81.1%). This is in accordance with the statement expressed by Soemirat (2009), that nutritional fulfillment factors determine the success of children in the learning process. Some parents only assume that if children study hard they will get relatively high learning outcomes. In fact, there are many other factors that influence children's learning outcomes, especially for students who are still sitting in low class. Where physical health is still very influential. Children who get good nutritional fulfillment from their families tend to be enthusiastic about learning and achievement.

Nutritional status research is a measurement based on anthropometric data and biochemistry and dietary history (Beck, 2000). School children, including vulnerable groups of nutrition that requires the fulfillment of nutrients because it can affect physical growth and brain development. This relates to the learning process and the achievement of optimal learning outcomes. Children who suffer from malnutrition will result in reduced catchment, decreased concentration of learning, physical growth is not optimal, tend to be short stature, the child is not actively moving, weak immune system so it is susceptible to disease and affects the work capacity as an adult. One of the factors that influence learning achievement is the level of intelligence. Intelligence is closely related to the level of growth and development of brain cells, and food influences the development of brain cells (Soemirat, 2009).

Research on the relationship of nutritional status with the learning outcomes of Grade 1 students at SD Negeri 5 Banda Aceh conducted by Rizki, et al (2017), shows the results that there is a relationship between nutritional status and learning outcomes of Grade 1 students at SD Negeri 5 Banda Aceh. Previous research conducted by Masdewi et al (2011) has proven that there is a significant relationship between eating behavior and nutritional status on learning achievement.

2. Interests

Based on the results of the statistical test the results show that elementary school students' learning interest towards learning achievement shows a p-value = 0,000 (<0.05), so it can be concluded that there is an influence of learning interest on elementary students' learning achievement. This is confirmed by the opinion of Djamarah (2002) which states

that "Interest in learning tends to produce high achievement, conversely lack of interest in learning will result in low learning achievement. A great interest in something is a big capital that means to achieve or obtain the object or object of interest. The emergence of interest in learning is caused by various things, partly because of a strong desire to get a good job and want to live happily and happily. While learning achievement is generally concerned with aspects of knowledge, while learning outcomes include aspects of character formation of students.

The word achievement is widely used in various fields and activities including in the arts, sports and education, especially learning ". If students want to get high achievements, these students have a high interest in learning. This is in accordance with the research of Supardi et al (2012) about interest which says "students who have high interest will tend to be diligent, resilient, enthusiastic in learning, never give up and happy to face challenges". This is very reasonable because to get high learning interest requires high perseverance. This proves indirectly learning achievement affects student learning habits. In other words, students who have good learning achievement will have good study habits. This proves the opinion of Aunurrahman (2009) Learning habits are the behavior of someone who has been embedded in a relatively long time so as to characterize the learning activities they do. Learning habits that are embedded in students can be seen in student learning activities and can be carried out continuously throughout the desired time. Study habits affect learning achievement, because student achievement is obtained by many factors which influence one of them is student learning habits. According to Shah (2001) in the book Educational Psychology with a New Approach explained that interest is a tendency and high enthusiasm or a great desire for something, one of which is an interest in learning. Meanwhile, according to Djaali (2008) interest is a feeling of preferability and interest in one thing or activity, without anyone asking.

Interest is basically the acceptance of a relationship between oneself and an outside self, the stronger or closer the relationship, the greater the interest in something. Meanwhile, Shaleh and Wahab (2004) said that "Interest is also interpreted as a tendency to pay attention and act towards people, activities or situations that are the object of these interests with a feeling of pleasure. Likewise for students if they are interested in one subject, then they will show in their learning achievement in school.

Big interest influence on learning, because if the learning material, learning facilities (facilities and infrastructure), the environmental situation is not in accordance with the interests of students, then the student concerned will not learn as well as possible due to the lack of attractiveness obtained by the student. Conversely, if the subject matter, facilities and infrastructure (facilities and infrastructure), the environmental situation is in accordance with the interests of students, then the interest in student learning will increase.

3. Motivation For Learning

Based on the results of the statistical test, the results show that learning motivation towards elementary school student learning achievement in the district of North Balikpapan

shows p -value = 0.412 (> 0.05) meaning that learning achievement is not influenced by children's learning motivation, and when viewed from learning motivation, the majority of student motivation is lacking (52.6%), but the majority of children continue to excel (81.1%). This is because some students will follow the lesson well if the teacher who teaches is their favorite teacher. If teachers rarely enter but only give assignments students are not motivated to follow the lessons even some do the work or ignore. This is consistent with the theory expressed by Uno (2011) "learning motivation is internal and external encouragement to students who are learning to conduct behavior, in general with several indicators or supporting elements. These indicators include: the desire and desire to succeed, encouragement and needs in learning, hopes and aspirations for the future, appreciation in learning, and a conducive learning environment. "Learning motivation determines perseverance in learning. A child who has been motivated to learn something tries to learn well and diligently in the hope of obtaining better results (Ahmad, 2013)

Motivation can also be said as a series of efforts to provide certain conditions, so that someone wants and wants to do something, and if he does not like it, then he will try to eliminate or avoid the feeling of dislike. So that motivation can be stimulated by external stimuli, but that motivation grows from within a person. In learning activities, motivation can be said to be the overall driving force in students that gives rise to learning activities, which ensures continuity of learning activities and which gives direction to learning activities, so that the desired goals of the learning subject can be achieved. Specifically, learning motivation is anything that is intended to encourage or encourage people who are doing learning activities to become even more active in their learning to obtain achievements.

Motivation can arise from outside or from within the individual itself. Motivation that comes from outside the individual is given by motivators such as his parents, teachers, counselors, close people, and others. While the motivation that comes from or arises in a person, can be caused by someone has a desire to be able to achieve something (ideals). If someone does not have the motivation to learn in themselves, then that person is difficult to get achievements in learning (Prawiro, 2009).

Based on the statistical test results obtained that the attitude of learning towards elementary school student learning achievement in the district of North Balikpapan shows p -value = 0.627 (> 0.05) meaning that student achievement is not influenced by attitude. When viewed from the attitude of learning, the majority of students' attitudes are moderate (80%), but the majority of children continue to excel (81.1%). According to Prajitno, et al (2002), attitude is a system consisting of cognitive components, feelings and tendencies to act. Attitude is a level of positive and negative feelings aimed at psychological objects. Attitude is part of human behavior as a symptom or picture of personality that radiates out. Thus attitudes are behaviors or actions resulting from one's reaction to other people or certain objects (Sudijono, 2008).

Ismaimuza (2010) in his research stated that Attitude is a condition of mental emotional readiness to take a particular action when a situation is faced. Attitude shows a person's condition to be ready to do something, not a real behavior. Every person has a different attitude towards an aphrodisiac. This is caused by several factors that exist in each individual, such as differences in talent, interests, experience, knowledge, intensity, feelings, and also the environmental situation.

4. Attitude

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In terms of learning, a student will be willing and determined to study or not depends on the attitudes and interests that exist in him. Attitudes and interests as psychological factors differ in their role in learning. In the process of learning, that attitude functions as "dynamic forces" that is as a force that will move people to learn. Whereas interest acts as "motivating forces", that is, as forces that will encourage students to learn. Sukmadinata (2005), explains that learning outcomes are the realization or expansion of potential skills or capacities a person has. Mastery of one's learning outcomes can be seen from their behavior, both in the form of mastery of knowledge, thinking skills and motor skills. Furthermore Sudjana (2010) defines that learning outcomes are changes in behavior. So it can be said that attitude does not have to be a determinant that a person will achieve, but it can be a dynamic process so that someone will change their behavior, then in the learning process learning outcomes are changes in student behavior that occur through the learning process.

5. Elementary school children's achievement

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V. CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

Based on the results of the analysis and discussion, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. Nutrition status of primary school children is mostly good nutrition (98.9%), only 1 child (1.1%) has a poor nutritional status.
2. The interest in learning for elementary school children is mostly medium (75.8%) and 24.2% interest in learning is moderate.
3. Motivation of learning of elementary school children (SD) is mostly lacking in learning (52.6%) and 47.4% of their learning motivation is moderate.
4. Learning attitudes of elementary school children (SD) are mostly medium (80.0%).
5. The learning achievement of elementary school children (SD) is mostly medium, namely 77 people (81.1%) and 18 people (18.9%) their learning achievement is less or below average.
6. The results of data analysis using log regression test obtained p-value <0.05, on the variables of interest and nutritional status.

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